

Ecological Engineering Integration: A PBL Journey Towards Sustainability in Rural Project Contexts

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062827>

Abstract

Amid the current challenges posed by climate change and human-induced environmental shifts, rural higher education plays a crucial role, serving as a dynamic platform to address diverse issues across various disciplines. Although education in rural areas is uneven, leading to significant gaps in the learning process and differences in educational content, it is a platform to introduce sustainability approaches. To address rural education, the Universidad Nacional de Colombia has a Special Admission Program using Problem-Based Learning (PBL). This four-term program aims to enhance both soft and hard skills through transversal projects. Being rural implies ecology as a central theme in several disciplines. Ecology prompts students to reflect deeply on their communities. PBL projects encourage students to explore multidisciplinary connections, seeking alternative solutions for their communities. Within this framework, ecology provides an excellent opportunity to examine different dimensions—economic, social, and environmental issues. The process begins by constructing a problem tree that encapsulates these challenges. Various tools, such as field trips and basic descriptive analyses of real situations, are then employed for in-depth study. Between 2022 and 2023, a total of 20 student projects were implemented. In the initial semester, students adopted an observational approach to familiarise themselves with their territories and refine their problem trees. Subsequent terms empowered students to conduct experiments within their communities, aiming to explore and address significant issues from a sustainable perspective grounded in an interdisciplinary. Among these projects, 15 utilised socio-ecological systems and maps, while three explored various strategies to enhance their understanding of sustainability through experiments and tools such as biodiversity catalogues and surveys in rural communities. This approach illustrates how engineering students can deepen their comprehension of their territories, acting as a guiding tool for their learning process and reflection on different problems within the special program, providing valuable tools for future academic projects.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning, Ecology, Sustainability Engineering, Rural Education

1 Introduction

Globally, young students typically demonstrate average proficiency levels in problem-solving abilities and numerical tasks. However, in Colombia, these skills exhibit significant disparities primarily driven by socioeconomic inequalities (OECD, 2022). Educational programs around the world face challenges in meeting the demand for graduates who possess the necessary knowledge and skills to tackle complex ecological issues in an ever-changing global landscape (Jalkanen et al., 2020; Lewinsohn et al., 2006). Students globally face challenges in integrating knowledge and addressing societal issues due to difficulty in memorization. Educators must prioritize critical thinking to cultivate future professionals capable of tackling global challenges. Sharing expert methods and encouraging practical skill development can deepen understanding of ecological processes (Nordlund, 2016). This prepares students for real-world application and interdisciplinary collaboration amidst unsustainable human practices and the urgent need for sustainability education outlined by the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (Klemow et al., 2024).

The learning process in universities encompasses two main components. Firstly, there's the aspect where students are actively involved in learning, which involves cognitive processes and individual functions. Secondly, instructors play a crucial role in engaging with students during the learning process, potentially

enhancing student learning outcomes. Various theories and research on learning highlight factors within classrooms that affect learning and teaching. These include principles such as Research-Based Smart Teaching, consideration of students' prior knowledge, understanding of how knowledge is structured, motivation, development of mastery skills, and integration of social, emotional, and intellectual interactions. Furthermore, the importance of students becoming self-directed learners, capable of regulating their own learning, is emphasized (Ambrose et al., 2010).

Active learning has been promoted as a method to bridge gaps in outcomes in STEAM disciplines, including ecology (Lewinsohn et al., 2006). Despite a strong reliance on lectures, there has been an increase in its use by instructors in recent years (Eagan et al., 2013). Receiving institutional backing for active learning methods is vital. The absence of administrative support becomes apparent in students feeling constrained due to insufficient physical learning environments and limited faculty training in active learning approaches (Foote, 2016). Achieving institutional commitment is a recognized challenge that requires adequate acknowledgment by academic institutions, which promotes the search for innovative teaching methods (Barr & Tagg, 1995; Cavanagh, 2016). Choosing an appropriate strategy can be facilitated by instructors exploring new teaching methods in ecological classrooms. This includes the promotion of active learning for STEAM instruction, such as problem-based learning, and providing comprehensive methodological overviews with practical implementation advice (Lewinsohn et al., 2015). Early career teachers encounter insufficient support for professional development, despite the pressing demands of time. However, collaborating with experienced colleagues proves invaluable in navigating these challenges (Gaulke et al., 2024).

Problem-Based learning emphasizes student-centered active learning through problem-solving activities driven by the quest for solutions (Savin-Banden & Howell, 2004). Relevant, realistic problems with inherent complexity enable students to explore various pathways and multiple valid solutions. Additionally, analysing solutions requires prior collaboration among students facilitated by an instructor (Balzano & Marzi, 2023; Barrows, 1980). Solutions may be multidisciplinary with different tools, enhancing students' soft skills and specific knowledge areas, teamwork, leadership, and social interaction fostering meaningful learning beyond the classroom (Brundiers & Arnim, 2013; Williams et al., 2010).

Theoretical underpinnings for problem-based learning stem from social constructivism, social development, and social interaction, where knowledge is formed through collaborative interaction tailored to the context (Savin-Banden & Howell, 2004; Vygotskii, 1978). The instructor's primary role is to facilitate learning by presenting meaningful problems and offering support as needed. Effective learning occurs when individuals are challenged with concepts slightly above their current level and are provided with the necessary assistance to grasp them. Cooperative learning theory further supports this approach by advocating for problem-based group work, which not only enhances achievement but also fosters critical thinking skills and promotes active engagement among (D'Avanzo, 2003). Evidence suggests significant gains in applied and process skills, student engagement, and applied knowledge assessment compared to traditional classrooms. It's essential for instructors to develop skills to effectively facilitate active learning, including problem-based learning (Gijbels et al., 2005).

The educational approach at Roskilde University, established in 1972, is characterized by interdisciplinary problem-oriented participant-directed project work, which has drawn attention from institutions across Europe. Known as Problem-Oriented Project Learning (OPPL), this framework emphasizes group work, the exemplary principle, and social relevance to create a dynamic learning environment. Through real-world problem-solving, students tackle scientific and social issues, prioritizing hands-on approaches over traditional assignments. Interdisciplinary collaboration allows flexibility in choosing theories and methods, enriching learning experiences, while the exemplary principle encourages students to explore specific problems for broader

insights. Within this structured curriculum, participant-directed learning and group work are pivotal for fostering collaboration and peer learning (Andersen & Heilesen, 2015a).

Derived from the theory that underpins Problem-Based Learning (PBL), PEAMA Sumapaz has designed its own model focused on rural and transdisciplinary education, which is called the Torca Model (Rodríguez-Mesa, 2022). The Torca model incorporates students from various programs who work together within the same framework, supported by two facilitators and teachers from the different subjects involved in the project. Each teacher enriches the students' perspectives, helping them to achieve the learning outcomes for each respective subject (Rodríguez-Mesa, 2023; Rodríguez-Mesa et al., 2023). One of the experiences includes pedagogical field trips focused on the recognition of the territory in some of the subjects and problems in the project-work.

2 Methods

This study will focus on presentations detailing a process undertaken between 2022 and 2023, showcasing projects designed by students. The objective is to illustrate how students formulate objectives rooted in ecological principles to address real community issues using engineering solutions. These discussions will draw from experiences in rural areas such as Sumapaz, Nazareth, Ciudad Bolívar, and Torca—rural communities around Bogotá, Colombia. In these areas, the Universidad Nacional de Colombia has enrolled new students in different academic programs for the first four semesters.

2.1 Area of study

The PEAMA Sumapaz program (PSP) began at the National University (Acuerdo 025, 2007) is a program aimed at students from rural areas. In 2016, in collaboration with the District Secretary of Education, the program was expanded to include graduates from all rural schools of Bogotá, creating the PSP (Resolución 405, 2016). This program focuses on improving reading, writing, and mathematics skills. This program uses the approach of PBL, in which they can improve as well as other fundamental subjects and soft skills that provide students with tools to elevate their academic level. Given the significant education disparities in rural areas, students from these regions are at a higher risk of dropping out. Therefore, the program serves as a framework to help reduce dropout rates. In Colombia, the dropout rates in higher education are alarmingly high, with nearly 12.84% of students affected (MEN, 2023) highlighting a significant challenge for education in rural areas. Program students complete the first four semesters of various degree programs, including Engineering, before transitioning to urban campuses in Bogotá to complete their studies.

The intention is for them to undertake their final projects in their home regions, addressing local challenges and contributing to regional development. It is important to note that the PSP campus is situated within the territory belonging to Locality 20 of Bogotá, which is part of the rural area of the capital of Colombia. In this context the discipline of ecology brings to students the opportunity to explore dimensions that compound their territory as environmental, economic and social aspects, which is an excellent platform for improving their academic abilities at the same time to know better their homes.

2.2 Project's structure

In the four semesters of the PSP, students undertake one project per semester within interdisciplinary groups comprising students from various fields. The initial two semesters focus on acquainting students with the region, exploring its key areas, some of which have been home to families for generations, fostering collaborative knowledge creation. This approach enables students to delve deeper into significant community issues. In the subsequent two semesters, students develop experimental designs, collect data on real-world challenges, and propose potential solutions, often in collaboration with community members, friends, and

relatives. The projects cover diverse problems, topics, and disciplines, allowing students to progressively enhance their understanding of the region and its environment, thereby evolving their project approach over time (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Project structure in PSP.

The project provides a structured framework for guiding students in interdisciplinary group work, featuring a written document and two oral presentations: one for the teaching staff and another for the community. The manuscript includes sections like context, problem statement, justification, research question, objectives, methodology, conceptual framework, results, and references. Students are encouraged to develop their conceptual framework early in the project, utilizing social, economic, and environmental research tools for information. They also utilize problem and solution trees to comprehensively understand and identify the problem.

It is important to note that in the latter semesters (third and fourth), students incorporate an additional component: a discussion of their results in the light of theory. At the end of each semester, students from all semesters are required to make presentations. These presentations are delivered to both professors and students and include a session for questions and answers. Furthermore, selected topics are presented to the community as part of an organized event in which community members can know more about the results and propose possible initial solutions.

2.3 Case study

In each subject within the program, teachers must align with the intended learning outcomes (ILOs) specified in the university's faculty syllabus. For instance, in the case of ecology, which falls under the Science Faculty and Biology Department, instructors select relevant topics from the syllabus that are applicable to the project's challenges. Ecology covers a range of essential topics, providing students with a comprehensive understanding of various issues. By adopting an approach that spans different scales, students explore knowledge related to their region. This exploration begins at the global level and progresses through regional, local, species, and organism levels. The ecological approach encompasses biogeochemical cycles, the flow of matter, ecosystem characteristics, and habitat features. Additionally, it considers the living environment of human communities and its connection to specific energy flux cases arising from their projects. Some of these cases involve describing energy flow in trophic webs and food chains, while others focus on interactions between species. These insights allow students and the community to better understand their environment and the fundamental structure and organization of life.

Figure 2. Ecological Perspective in Engineering Education.

3 Results

During the period spanning 2022 to 2024, students from various academic programs undertook different projects that took ecology as a transversal subject in the first semester. There are different careers in this sample, encompassing disciplines such as electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, electric engineering, mechatronic engineering, and agronomic engineering. It is important to mention that these projects involved collaboration with varied fields including social work, biology, business management, architecture, and anthropology.

3.1 Types of projects

During this period, a total of 20 projects involving 115 students were completed, yielding various outcomes. The analysis of these projects utilized categories of green technologies, recognizing their crucial role in achieving global and local development goals. These goals aim to mitigate negative consequences and promote environmental sustainability by integrating solutions that consider the environment, economy, and society (Guo et al., 2020). Within these categories, key issues pertaining to sustainable engineering were identified, including Education, Environmental Management and Conservation, Mobility and Transportation, Water, Loss of Traditional Knowledge, and Education.

Table 1. Problems and dimensions of the ecological perspective, the number of students and projects 2022-2023.

Education	20
Social	10
Social, environmental	10
Environmental Management and Conservation	58
Social, environmental	7
Social, environmental, economical	21
Social, environmental, technological	12
Social, environmental, technological, economical	18
Loss of Traditional Knowledge	7
Social, environmental, technological	7
Mobility and Transportation	3
Social, economical, technological	3
Territorial Planning	3
Social, environmental	3
Water	14
Social, environmental, economical	3
Social, environmental, technological	5
Social, environmental, technological, economical	6
Total general	105

3.2 Rubric of evaluation

The evaluation rubric is grounded in an outcomes-based approach, emphasizing what each student will know and be able to do upon completing a course. These approaches align with teaching and learning activities outlined in the department's syllabus. Importantly, the evaluation process is based on the SOLO taxonomy (Biggs et al., 1982). SOLO (Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes) provides educators with a systematic method for designing curriculum, formulating learning objectives, and assessing student performance. Within this taxonomy, six key cognitive levels are identified: 1) knowledge, 2) comprehension, 3) application of knowledge, 4) analysis, 5) synthesis and 6) critical thinking. The rubric also incorporates elements from other authors, such as the assessment of intended learning outcomes (ILOs) which draw from Bloom's Taxonomy at various levels. Learning in this domain involves adaptation and reorganization, potentially leading to both specific and generalized experiences, and is assessed through the application, selection, and treatment of problems (Andersen & Heilesen, 2015b).

3.3 PBL in groups skills

During ecological activities, student groups exhibit diverse dynamics while utilizing tools such as cartography and community surveys. Seminars in ecology serve as platforms for presenting theoretical frameworks relevant to projects, involving a thorough review of pertinent literature. Subsequently, students delve into practical tasks, designing optimal methods for gathering information from their respective territories. Collaborating within groups, they engage in discussions and reach agreements to achieve desired outcomes. Furthermore, workshops explore the functioning of different habitats within communities. Some workshops specifically focus on sustainability elements across economic, social, and ecological domains. The overarching goal is to construct meaningful relationships between these domains in the context of the chosen problem.

3.4 Challenges

There are various challenges associated with this method. One of the most significant challenges is ensuring that students effectively collaborate in groups. Although students may reach agreements to achieve outcomes, it is crucial to ensure that they adhere to these agreements and make progress toward their goals. At times, students may struggle to organize tasks and meet deadlines for project submissions. In such cases, it is important to provide support through collaboration with other professionals, psychological support, and facilitators to assist with their activities. Additionally, a chancellor can play a crucial role in connecting with the community.

4 Discussion

The objective of this study is to illustrate how students formulate objectives rooted in ecological principles to address real community issues using engineering solutions. In this case study based on problem-based learning (PBL), several key findings emerge. First, the interplay between ecology and engineering plays a crucial role in fostering sustainability initiatives that address environmental challenges. Second, the methodology increases awareness of environmental problems. Third, the evaluation rubric emphasizes that students will acquire knowledge and skills by completing the course syllabus. Additionally, PBL contributes to the development of group skills, as students engage in discussions, reach agreements, and achieve desired outcomes. However, students also encounter difficulties when analysing community problems and striving to meet the defined objectives.

The integration of ecological principles and engineering practices within project-based learning (PBL) holds promise for advancing sustainability initiatives. Our research findings align with (Lavado-Anguera et al., 2024), who emphasize the critical need for interdisciplinary collaboration. By bridging ecological understanding and

engineering solutions, students gain a holistic perspective on environmental challenges. However, further research is warranted to explore specific strategies for optimizing this interplay. While environmental management and conservation receive significant attention, other areas such as territorial planning and mobility remain less explored. Notably, the process of social learning within sustainable development can effectively inform projects implemented by both the public and private sectors, connecting teaching and research with real-world needs and problems (Cazorla-Montero et al., 2019). Over time, students may identify additional real-world challenges based on their knowledge of the local context and interactions with people.

Project-based learning (PBL) effectively heightens students' awareness of environmental issues. Through engagement in real-world projects, students grapple with complex problems, deepening their understanding of ecological dynamics. Future studies should explore the long-term impact of this heightened awareness on students' environmental consciousness. Notably, this study highlights specific PBL projects that introduce students to real-world ecological problems. The research findings align with the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale, emphasizing interdisciplinary collaboration and engagement. In a rural context, possible alternatives are proposed, emphasizing the importance of working with other disciplines for enriching discussions about the problem and potential solutions (Nanni & Allan, 2020). Through active engagement in real-world projects, project-based learning (PBL) offers opportunities to tackle complex environmental challenges and connect sustainability knowledge with positive environmental behaviours (Bramwell-Lalor et al., 2020).

Collaborative learning lies at the heart of project-based learning (PBL). Lavado-Anguera et al. (2024) emphasize the significance of negotiation, teamwork, and effective communication during PBL. Students actively participate in discussions, reach consensus, and collectively strive toward desired outcomes. To optimize group dynamics, educators can explore strategies for managing conflicts, fostering inclusivity, and promoting collaboration within project teams. Organizing work based on prior agreements becomes crucial to ensure alignment with goals. As students gain experience, their understanding of teamwork evolves, leading to more refined agreements over time.

PBL goes beyond rote memorization, allowing students to develop research skills. Our findings align with emphasizing the application and comprehension of ecological concepts. Encouraging students to explore real-world data, conduct fieldwork, and engage in inquiry-based learning can further enhance their research capabilities (Almulla, 2020). Despite the benefits, students encounter difficulties when analysing community problems and meeting defined objectives. Acknowledge these challenges, emphasizing the need for alignment with real-world complexities. Addressing these obstacles requires ongoing support, mentorship, and adaptive pedagogical strategies.

Projects in ecology and engineering serve as linchpins in promoting sustainable development by integrating ecological principles with engineering practices. In this symbiotic relationship, ecology provides a foundation of understanding regarding ecosystems, biodiversity, and the intricate interconnections within natural systems. Engineers leverage this ecological knowledge to design innovative solutions that mitigate environmental impact, conserve resources, and promote resilience. By incorporating ecological considerations into engineering projects, such as sustainable infrastructure design, renewable energy systems, and waste management solutions, practitioners can enhance sustainability outcomes (Dale et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the importance of rural education in Colombia cannot be overstated, particularly given the disparities and challenges that rural communities face. Addressing these educational gaps is paramount for fostering social equity, economic development, and environmental stewardship. Effective rural education initiatives can empower local populations with the knowledge and skills needed to engage in sustainable

practices, contribute to community development, and address pressing environmental issues unique to rural areas. Thus, integrating ecological principles into engineering projects and prioritizing rural education initiatives are essential strategies for advancing sustainability efforts and promoting holistic development in Colombia.

5 Conclusion

The collaborative efforts of students across diverse academic disciplines from 2021 to 2024 underscore the importance of interdisciplinary approaches in addressing contemporary challenges. Through projects spanning fields like electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, mechatronic engineering, and agronomic engineering, students have demonstrated the value of cross-disciplinary collaboration in fostering innovation and problem-solving. Furthermore, the engagement of other fields such as social work, biology, business management, architecture, and anthropology highlight the interconnectedness of knowledge domains in tackling complex issues. By leveraging diverse perspectives and expertise, students have not only expanded their own skill sets but also contributed to holistic solutions that address societal, environmental, and technological needs. This period exemplifies the power of interdisciplinary collaboration in driving progress and advancing sustainable development goals.

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